

INFLUENCE OF MWCNTS ON MECHANICAL AND INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER /EPOXY FILAMENT WOUND COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The liquid-like reactive multi-walled carbon nanotubes (r-MWCNTs) was prepared and added in epoxy matrix. Then the epoxy matrix containing 0.5wt% r-MWCNTs was reinforced by T700 carbon fibers and the NOL-rings were prepared on a filament winding machine. The wettability of the uncured epoxy was evaluated by measuring the surface energy and viscosity. It was demonstrated that the epoxy with r-MWCNTs exhibited much better wettability than that of pristine epoxy. After adding 0.5 wt% r-MWCNTs, the tensile strength, tensile modulus, elongation and interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of NOL-rings were significantly enhanced, respectively, compared to the pristine epoxy composites. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) studies revealed that the addition of r-MWCNTs could improve the interfaces bonding between T700 carbon fiber and epoxy matrix. The dynamic mechanical analysis results also showed that the glass transition temperature of the composites increased by about 16°C after the addition of 0.5wt% r-MWCNTs.

1 INTRODUCTION

The T700 carbon fiber/epoxy composite is a kind of advanced material that has many promising applications in the fields of aerospace, military industry and general industry owing to the outstanding mechanical and thermal properties. However, the interfacial adhesion of T700 carbon fiber composites is not good enough for practical uses due to the smooth surface morphology of carbon fibers¹. As a result of their excellent mechanical, thermal, optical and electrical properties, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have attracted worldwide attention since their discovery in 1991 [1-5]. Unique atomic structure, very high aspect ratio, low density and extraordinary mechanical performance make them ideal reinforcing fillers in composites. Many researches have been conducted into developing high-performance CNT-filled polymer composites to fully exploit the potential of CNTs [6-9]. However, it is reported that there is only marginal improvement or even decrease in mechanical properties of nanocomposites after adding commercial CNTs into epoxy matrices as a result of their aggregation and lacking of interfacial adhesion with matrices [10,11]. In the recent years, many progresses have been made by researchers to improve the dispersion of CNTs and interfacial bonding with the matrices [12,13]. One method is the functionalization of commercial CNTs. A large number of methods for chemical functionalization of CNTs, either at the tips or sidewalls of them, have been attempted or employed [14-16]. And amino functionalization has been proved to be preferable than other surface treatment methods in improving CNTs dispersion and bonding with epoxy matrices [17-20].

In fact, the combination of the nano-reinforcement and other traditional reinforcement will lead to the potential development of a new generation of hybrid composite materials with extraordinary behavior for both applications and fundamental science mechanisms[21]. In this work, the commercial MWCNTs were chemically functionalized and then r-MWCNTs were prepared. On the basis of uniform dispersion of r-MWCNTs in epoxy matrix, the three phase hybrid composites were prepared

by filament winding of T700 carbon fibers. The effects of r-MWCNTs on the wettability of the epoxy matrix to T700 carbon fiber as well as the mechanical and thermo-mechanical properties of the composites were studied in this paper.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) produced by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method were purchased from Shenzhen Nanotech Port Co, Ltd (purity >95%). Butyl glycidyl ether (BGE), obtained from Aldrich chemical Co., was used as reactive diluents. The alicyclic glycidyl ether type epoxy resin (TDE-85) was provided by Tianjin Jindong chemical factory (epoxy value, 0.85, Molecular formula is shown in Figure 1). The curing agent, diethyl toluene diamine (DETDA, Aldrich chemical Co.) and 3'Dimethyl-4, 4' Diamino diacyclohexyl methane (DMDC, Aldrich chemical Co.) were used as received. T700 carbon fibers were obtained from Toray Company, Japan.

Figure 1: Molecular formula of TDE-85 epoxy resin.

2.2 Functionalization of the MWCNTs

The procedures used to functionalize MWCNTs were described in Figure 2. The commercial MWCNTs (3 g) were dispersed in 400mL mixture of concentrated sulfuric and nitric acids (3:1 by volume). After being sonicated for 1h at room temperature, the mixture was stirred for 80 min at 80 °C. Then the CNTs were cleaned continuously with deionized water until chemically neutral. After that, the carboxylated MWCNTs (c-MWCNTs) were dried in vacuum for 12 h at 80 °C. The c-MWCNTs (2 g) were stirred in 100 mL of a 20:1 mixture of thionyl chloride (SOCl₂) and dimethylformamide (DMF) at 70 °C for 24 h. After the acyl chlorination, SOCl₂ and DMF were removed through vacuum distillation. The MWCNTs were washed by THF fully and dried for 1 h at room temperature in vacuum. The gained MWCNTs reacted with the mixture of ethylenediamine and DMF (110 mL, 10:1 in volume ratio) at 110 °C for 96 h with the protection of N₂. Then wash the mixture using THF and vacuum-filter through Millipore PTFE membranes. After dried in vacuum at 70 °C for 12 h, the amino-functionalized MWCNTs (r-MWCNTs) were obtained [22].

Figure 2: Schematic of chemical functionalization for MWCNTs.

The a-MWCNTs (1.5 g) were first mixed with 100ml of butyl glycidyl ether (BGE), and then treated using a digital sonifier operating at 400 W for 2 h in an ice bath. After the a-MWCNTs reacted with BGE, the excessive solution was removed in a hot vacuum oven at 70 °C until the weight ratio of MWCNTs and BGE decreased to 1:7, then the r-MWCNTs/diluents blend was obtained.

2.3 Composites preparation

The resin matrices were made from TDE-85 epoxy resin and curing agent which was composed of DETDA and DMDC with a weight ratio of 3:1. The r-MWCNTs were dispersed into the epoxy by stirring 12 h at 60 °C and then sonicating the mixture for 2 h at 60 °C. The curing agent (30 wt %) was added into the obtained black mixture and agitated for 30 min at 25°C. After degassed in a vacuum oven, the mixture was used for testing of the surface energy and viscosity. The NOL rings were wound using a filament winding machine (MAW-20-LS1-6, Mikrosam Ltd) with 7N tension at 35 °C. The NOL rings were cured at 80 °C for 1h and 120 °C for 2 h, following a post curing at 150 °C for 2 h.

2.4 Characterizations

FTIR(8700, Nicolet Ltd, USA) was applied to confirm the functionalization of the MWCNTs. The commercial MWCNTs, c-MWCNTs and a-MWCNTs were separately mixed with KBr powder and compressed to a disc-shaped specimen for FTIR analysis.

A tension meter DSA 100 (KRUSS Ltd. Germany) was used to measure the surface energy of two uncured epoxy samples via a platinum plate. In this experiment, the platinum plate was put into the epoxy resin and the surface energy was obtained by measuring the force on the microbalance. Surface energy of uncured epoxy samples were measured from 20 °C to 60 °C. The viscosity was measured by SNB-1 Digital LCD Viscometer (Shanghai Nirun Intelligent Technology Co., Ltd.) at the different temperature. The data presented in the current work are the averages of three replicate measurements.

The Instron 1211 machine (Instron Ltd., England) was applied to measure tensile strength and interlaminar shear strength of T700 carbon/epoxy NOL-rings according to the ASTM D2290-00 and ASTM D2344/D2344M-00.

The FE-SEM (Supra 55, Zeiss, Germany) was applied to investigate the interfacial bonding between the T700 carbon fiber and the nano-filled matrix through observing the structure and morphology of the fracture surface. Each sample was coated with Pt before SEM image observation.

The thermo-mechanical properties of the composites were characterized by DMA Q800 (TA Instruments, USA) mounted with a dual cantilever mode. The temperature ramp was 3 °C/min and the frequency was 1Hz.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 FTIR analysis of MWCNTs

Figure 3 shows the FTIR spectra of commercial MWCNTs, c-MWCNTs and a-MWCNTs. In Figure 3(b), the absorption peaks at 1701 and 3430.4 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the carboxylic C=O and O–H stretching vibration, which means the carboxylic acid groups have been attached to the nanotubes successfully after acid treatment. In Figure 3 (c), the peak for the N–H stretching vibrations of amine groups appeared at 3421 cm⁻¹. The result demonstrates that the amine functionalization of MWCNTs was carried out successfully.

Figure 3: FT-IR spectra: (a) commercial MWCNTs, (b) c-MWCNTs, (c) a-MWCNTs.

3.2 The effects of reactive carbon nanotubes on wettability

The interface plays a vital role in stress transfer from one fiber to another in the matrix of a composite. An adequate wetting is required for taking advantage of the excellent mechanical properties of T700 carbon fibers in composites. In general, the wettability of polymer matrix on the surface of a fiber could be characterized by the surface energy and the viscosity of the matrix. In practice, the wettability of the fiber reinforcement in the matrix can be improved by decreasing the surface energy and the viscosity of the uncured matrix.

Figure 4: The surface energy of epoxy resin.

Figure 5: The viscosity of epoxy resin.

The surface energy of different samples is given in Figure 4. The surface energy of all the matrices decreased with increased temperature, which indicates the wettability would be improved at a higher processing temperature. Sample without r-MWCNTs had a higher surface tension compared to matrix with 0.5 wt% r-MWCNTs. The surface energy demonstrated a decrease of more than 10 mJ/m² after adding 0.5 wt% r-MWCNTs.

As shown in Figure 5, the viscosity of resin decreased as the rising of temperature. When the temperature was below 30 °C, the viscosity of the pure epoxy was lower than sample containing 0.5 wt% r-MWCNTs. As the temperature rising, the viscosity gap between samples with or without r-

MWCNTs got smaller and smaller. when the temperature was higher than 30 °C, the viscosity of the two samples almost got to the same value. As a result, the addition of r-MWCNTs was effective to decrease the surface energy of epoxy while there was no obvious influence on viscosity of resin at a temperature above 30 °C. And the contact angles between the epoxy and T700 carbon fibers became smaller by adding 0.5 wt% r-MWCNTs. In general, The processing temperature of resin composites is often higher than 30 °C, and the r-MWCNTs can improve the wettability of the epoxy to the T700 carbon fiber.

3.3 The effects of reactive carbon nanotubes on mechanical properties

The mechanical performances of T700 carbon fiber composites were measured, and the results are summarized in Table.1. After adding 0.5 % r-MWCNTs, the tensile strength of the NOL-ring was raised by 8.9%, from 2130 to 2320 MPa. The tensile modulus was enhanced by 12.2%, from 1310 to 1470 MPa. The interfacial shear strength was improved by 16.9%, which is clear evidence of better interface adhesion between the fiber and the matrix by adding 0.5 wt% r-MWCNTs. And the results are also agreeable with the wettability characterization. The epoxy containing r-MWCNTs wetted the fiber more fully and exhibited better interfacial bonding than that of pure epoxy.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of T700 carbon fiber NOL- rings

	Tensile strength (GPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Elongation (%)	ILSS (MPa)
Neat epoxy	2.13±0.31	1.31±0.28	2.19±0.11	69.6±0.89
0.5wt% r-MWCNTs	2.32±0.26	1.47±0.27	2.23±0.18	81.4±0.98

Figure 6: The microstructure of T700 carbon/epoxy composites: (a) Neat epoxy, (b) epoxy matrix with 0.5wt% r-MWCNTs.

As shown in Figure 6, the interface adhesion between the T700 carbon fiber and the matrix was enhanced remarkably after adding 0.5 wt% r-MWCNTs. In Figure 6 (a), the smooth surface of carbon fibers was displayed which denoted the poor interface adhesion between the fiber and matrix. While in Figure 6 (b), in the fracture surface a large number of resin remained on the surface of carbon fibers, which may indicate the strong interfacial bonding between the T700 carbon fibers and the epoxy matrix in the composites.

3.4 The effects of r-MWCNTs on thermo-mechanical properties

The effect of the r-MWCNTs on the dynamic mechanical property of the T700 carbon fiber/epoxy composites was analyzed by DMA in the experiment. The storage modulus (E') and the loss factor ($\tan \delta$) of the T700 carbon fiber/epoxy composites were characterized as functions of temperature. As shown in Figure 7(a), an obvious increment of the storage modulus was observed in the test temperature range after adding r-MWCNTs, which is consistent with the increased tensile modulus of composites. The r-MWCNTs can enhance the stiffness of the epoxy matrix which induced an increment of storage modulus of the composites.

At the same time, the addition of r-MWCNTs has affected the glass transition temperature (T_g) of resulting composites (Figure 7(b)). The T_g exhibited a shift from 186°C to 202°C as a result of the addition of r-MWCNTs. This phenomenon can be attributed to the stronger interfacial interaction in the composites containing r-MWCNTs, which restrained the movement of polymer chains.

(a)

(b)

Figure7: Storage modulus (a) and loss factor (b) of T700 carbon composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The commercial MWCNTs were converted into liquid-like r-MWCNTs by the chemical process. The experimental results on the surface energy and viscosity of epoxy resins demonstrated that the r-MWCNTs could improve the wettability of the epoxy to the T700 carbon fiber. The tensile strength, tensile modulus, elongation and ILSS of T700 carbon fiber/TDE-85 epoxy resin composite NOL-rings increased due to the addition of the r-MWCNTs. Fracture morphology observation showed that the interfacial adhesion between T700 carbon fiber/epoxy composites has been improved. At the same time, the epoxy containing r-MWCNTs possessed an enhanced T_g and storage modulus in the glass region.

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